

1 **Silencing of class I MHC in human p53 mutant tumors.**

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6 We studied expression of genes important for antigen presentation in tumors isolated from humans with
7 breast cancer. We compared total tumor transcriptome based on p53 status: wild-type, or containing
8 mutations in exon 3 of the p53 gene. We found silencing of class I MHC receptors in p53 mutant breast
9 cancers. In vitro, depletion of p53 with a small hairpin resulted in selective silencing of HLA-E, while
10 expression of a dominant negative point mutant, p53 R175H, did not and only resulted in weak repression
11 of HLA-F. Even within patients with wild-type p53, reduced expression of class I HLA receptors including
12 HLA-E was strongly associated with more rapid death. Together we demonstrate that loss of expression
13 resulting from deletion of a tumor suppressor or expression of a mutant tumor suppressor variant are
14 associated with different class I MHC tumor gene expression, and describe tumor gene expression
15 indicative of defective class I MHC responses.
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